

Metropolitan Transformation: Analysing Urban Cluster Dynamics in the Mebidangro Region

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Abstract

The Mebidangro metropolitan area, encompassing Medan, Binjai, Deli Serdang, and Karo, provides a snapshot of Indonesia's complex metropolitan development. Designated a National Strategic Area, Mebidangro is crucial for national development. Still, rapid and poorly coordinated urban expansion has strained infrastructure, driven land-use changes, and widened urban-rural spatial disparities. This study examines cluster changes in the 52 sub-districts within the Mebidangro metropolitan area from 2005 to 2023, using quantitative, descriptive, and spatial analyses to identify four main cluster types: urban core, suburban transition, peri-urban areas, and agricultural-specific zones. Findings indicate that the urban core has expanded significantly while the transition zone has shrunk, indicating metropolitan consolidation and the limited success of current spatial plans in controlling growth. The study recommends enhancing regional competitiveness through improved accessibility, reliable connectivity, and stronger human resource capacity in agriculture and tourism. It also calls for future efforts to assess the implementation of metropolitan planning and to build collaborative governance for equitable and balanced urban development.

Keywords: *Mebidangro, metropolitan, urbanization, urban cluster, sustainable development.*

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Introduction

The practical conditions in the area where the development is driven are not in line with what was planned. The planned urban area has expanded significantly in response to market demand. The urban form, in essence, refers to the spatial organization of human activities, along with the physical makeup of the city, which is formed by the interconnectedness of various components, such as land use, housing, population density, infrastructure, public facilities, and transportation and communication systems (Bettencourt, 2021a). Spatial structures may develop more rapidly than expected, resulting from demographic shifts, economic dynamics, socio-political influences, and cultural developments in various geographical contexts (Abrantes et al., 2017). In the Mebidangro Urban Area, rapid urban expansion has led to a significant transformation in land use. However,

these changes often result in inefficient and suboptimal spatial utilization, leading to overlapping interests and tensions across sectors and administrative boundaries.

The Metropolitan Mebidangro area, which includes Medan, Binjai, Deli Serdang, and Karo on the island of Sumatra, has experienced rapid development in recent decades. As one of the main metropolitan areas in Indonesia, Medan exhibits very rapid urbanization dynamics, encompassing economic, social, and cultural aspects. The urbanization process in this region increased the population and led to significant changes in the socio-economic structure and spatial management. (Long et al., 2007; Scherbina et al., 2021; Webster, 2014). Mebidangro, renowned for its economic and social ties between cities, plays a crucial role as a growth center in the northern part of the island of Sumatra. The inter-district linkage leads to an increasingly large and complex metropolitan area, ultimately challenging the government and regional management bodies in controlling development.

Despite its high growth, the Mebidangro region also faces the problem of uneven regional development. Regulations such as Presidential Regulation No. 62 of 2011, which concerns the Spatial Planning of the Medan, Binjai, Deli Serdang, and Karo Urban Areas, and Government Regulation No. 13 of 2017, which amends Government Regulation No. 26 of 2008 regarding the National Spatial Planning, categorize it as a National Strategic Area. In this regard, the Mebidangro region is crucial from the perspectives of defense, economy, social aspects, culture, and the carrying capacity of natural resources and the environment. Defining Mebidangro as a national strategic area creates efforts to accelerate development related to these interests. However, despite the region's great potential, several significant challenges remain, specifically the imbalance in development and dependence on diverse economic sectors (Martins & Santos Pereira, 2019; Webster, 2014). The dynamics and transformation of urban structures in the Mebidangro area need to be analyzed before and after it is officially designated as a strategic metropolitan area.

The main challenges facing cities within the Mebidangro metropolitan area include the complexity of city management amidst increasing population growth and heterogeneous regional conditions. Rapid urbanization is generally unplanned in line with rising living standards, posing a significant challenge to urban planning policies (Hudalah, Winarso, & Woltjer, 2007; Webster, 2014; Woltjer, 2014). Mebidangro, as a rapidly developing urban area, also strives to maintain its agrarian characteristics, similar to Jakarta, which is experiencing composite socio-economic changes. Land use patterns blur the distinction between rural and urban areas due to conurbation (Haryo Winarso, Hudalah, & Firman, 2015). With the rapid development of suburban areas, even their social and physical character is changing, shifting from rural to urban functions. This trend creates new jobs, accelerating spatial segregation in the area (Tong, Zhang, MacLachlan, & Li, 2020). The main challenges facing cities within the Mebidangro metropolitan area include the complexity of city management amidst increasing population growth and heterogeneous regional conditions. Rapid urbanization is generally unplanned in line with rising living standards, posing a significant challenge to urban planning policies (Webster, 2014; Woltjer, 2014). Mebidangro, as a rapidly developing urban area, also strives to maintain its agrarian characteristics, similar to Jakarta, which is experiencing composite socio-economic changes. Land use patterns blur the distinction between rural and urban areas due to conurbation (Haryo Winarso et al., 2015). With the rapid development of suburban areas, even the social and physical character of these areas is changing, shifting from rural to urban functions. This trend creates new jobs, accelerating spatial segregation in the area (Tong et al., 2020).

A literature review shows that rural-urban migration is a phenomenon that has brought about unexpected changes in people's lives (Gurumukhi, 2000). Rural-urban migration has reportedly increased rapidly to uncontrolled levels, leading to unchecked development, land fragmentation, destruction of natural habitats, and a decline in the quality of residential environments (Schwick,

Kienast, & Jaeger, 2010). As McGee expressed in 1991, the term “urbanization” refers to the combination of urban and rural forces that produce uncertainty in the border region. This urbanization process is increasingly evident in the Mebidangro area, where urban and rural life often mix, thus posing challenges in spatial planning and sustainable settlement management. Some studies indicate that metropolitan areas with polycentric systems, i.e., regions featuring multiple economic activity centers, tend to have higher per capita incomes and lower poverty rates than monocentric metropolitan areas (Arribas-bel & Sanz-gracia, 2014). This suggests that developing multiple growth centers in urban areas can enhance resource distribution and improve the quality of life within the community. However, in practice, the development of inter-city interaction in Indonesia, as shown by (H Winarso, 2011; Haryo Winarso et al., 2015) There is a tendency for intercity interaction in Indonesia to expand in terms of city size, but this is not in line with improving the quality of life of the people equally. This social and spatial inequality necessitates a new approach to designing and managing residential systems in metropolitan areas.

On the other hand, the settlement-related literature identifies fundamental differences between urban and rural settlements, with population being the main difference (Scherbina et al., 2021). These differences lead to challenges in designing settlement systems that can accommodate the needs of growing urban communities without neglecting existing rural areas. In the context of Mebidangro, an analysis of the region’s urban transformation reveals that designing a settlement system integrating urban and rural elements is crucial to support sustainable growth.

Although a substantial body of literature discusses various aspects of metropolitan area development, a gap remains in comparative studies on the development of integrated residential systems between urban and rural areas. One study (Abrantes et al., 2017) Has at least three main perspectives in assessing urban patterns, the first is the classical perspective that relies on the analysis of bivariate and multivariate statistical indicators, the second is the perspective based on GIS geocomputing and remote sensing since the 1990s, and the third is the multidimensional perspective that connects the previous approach, spatial metrics to analyse indicators and configurations related to urban patterns. Therefore, the author considers that to identify the development of the Mebidangro Metropolitan sub-district is not enough just a statistical approach, but must be characterized by the representation of indicators that describe the physical form of the city, where socio-economic demographic characteristics, land use variables, and infrastructure are configured enough to answer the research question. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the comparative development of the settlement system in the Mebidangro area before and after its designation as a metropolitan strategic area. This research will examine the impact of changes in the area’s status on its social, economic, and physical environmental systems.

The purpose of this study is to gain a better understanding of the transformation of urban form in Metropolitan Mebidangro, focusing on the development of settlement systems before and after the area’s status was transformed by the ratification of the national policy designating it as the Mebidangro National Strategic Area. This study seeks to explain urban transformation from 2005 to 2023 based on social, economic, and physical environmental factors, and it offers policy suggestions to help manage a sustainable metropolitan city. Through this method, solutions are expected to be achieved to improve the community’s quality of life in the metropolitan area of Mebidangro and to assist in the planning and management of appropriate metropolitan areas in Indonesia.

Materials and Methods

This study analyses the growth of the urban system in Mebidangro, which includes the cities of Medan, Binjai, Deli Serdang, and Karo. This study involves a significant urban area experiencing

rapid socio-economic and physical changes, primarily driven by urbanization and population growth. This article explains how this study connects the representation of contemporary urban processes in Mebidangro by combining classical statistical analysis and data collection with K-means cluster analysis and thematic mapping.

Study Area and Scope

The Mebidangro Metropolitan Urban Area covers a vast geographical region, spanning 52 sub-districts in total. It includes the entire city of Medan, with its 21 sub-districts; the whole town of Binjai, comprising five sub-districts; the full area of Deli Serdang Regency, with 22 sub-districts; and part of Karo Regency, with four sub-districts. The total area of Mebidangro is 301,697 hectares. This area is strategically significant, as it is a central economic and socio-cultural hub in Northern Sumatra (see Figure 1).

The research is situated within a broader framework that examines the effects of rapid urbanization on physical infrastructure, population density, migration patterns, and the socio-economic status of residents. Figure 2 illustrates the research flow that begins with problem formulation and a literature review to understand related theories. Furthermore, research variables were developed to analyze the phenomenon being studied. After that, data is collected through field checks and interviews. The collected data is then analyzed by creating thematic maps and comparing them between 2005 and 2023. The final stage uses K-means cluster analysis to group data based on characteristic similarity, allowing pattern identification and time comparison. This process results in a deeper understanding of the research topic being analyzed.

Figure 1. Mebidangro Metropolitan Area

Research Design

The study utilizes a classical approach to multivariate statistical analysis. Cluster analysis is the primary method used as an interdependent multivariate statistical approach to group data. Where each data set (sub-district) is considered to have similar values. This approach has also been used by other researchers in designing rural-urban typologies, including. (Handayani, 2013; Raharja, Aji, & Syarifudin, 2020; Rusu, 2015; Zhou, Xu, Radke, & Mu, 2004). Similarly, this study facilitates

understanding the transformation of sub-districts into activity centers in the Mebidangro Metropolitan area.

Figure 2. The Research Flow

This analysis process helps organize and identify the characteristics of each cluster. The following are the procedures to follow when conducting cluster analysis. This section provides a brief explanation of each step applied in this study.

1) Determination of operational variables. Data quality is also checked to identify variables beyond those generally used in assessing village-city transformation. Data quality considerations include data scale, data distribution, and data normality. This perspective is essential for understanding the relationship between the leading indicators of urban transformation, including social, economic, and physical factors, which result from a synthesis of theoretical studies often used by previous researchers (see Table 1). The approach also facilitates the identification of urban transformation patterns, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of how these factors interact to shape the development of the Mebidangro area.

Table 1. Key Urban Transformation Indicators

Factor	Indicator	Code	Criteria Assumptions	Source
Social Factors	Population Growth	PG	The increase in population, particularly in peri-urban areas, is often a result of migration and natural growth. Urban development drives expansion and can strain infrastructure and services.	(Handayani, 2013; Haryo Winarso et al., 2015)
	Migration Patterns	MP	Economic opportunities, better living conditions, or socio-political factors drive people to move from rural to urban or peri-urban areas.	(Handayani, 2013; Woltjer, 2014)
	Education Levels	EL	Most of the population has higher educational attainment, influencing	(Handayani, 2013)

			employment and economic participation in peri-urban areas.	
Economic Factors	Employment Structure	ES	The shift from rural agricultural (%) employment to urban industrial and service sector jobs. This transformation is central to the socio-economic changes in peri-urban areas.	(Woltjer, 2014; Yang, Liu, Li, & Du, 2018)
	Industrial and Service Sector Contribution to GDP	IC	The economy is primarily based on the industrial and service sectors, rather than agriculture. The shift towards these sectors is a defining feature of peri-urban economic transformation.	(Handayani, 2013; Haryo Winarso et al., 2015)
	Land Price Growth	LP	The increasing land prices in peri-urban areas are due to urban sprawl and increased demand for housing, infrastructure, and industrial space.	(H Dadashpoor & Ahani, 2019; Farah, Khan, Maan, Shahbaz, & Cheema, 2019; Haryo Winarso et al., 2015)
Physical Factors	Built-up Area Expansion	BU	The physical expansion of urban areas into previously rural zones leads to urban sprawl.	(Abrantes et al., 2017; Dadashpoor & Ahani, 2019; de la Barrera et al., 2016; Pickett et al., 2011; Schwick et al., 2010)
	Infrastructure Development	ID	The construction and improvement of infrastructure, such as roads, electricity, and water systems in peri-urban areas, often lag behind the rapid physical growth.	(Farah et al., 2019; Salvati & Zitti, 2017)
	Land Use Change	LuC	Converting agricultural land or natural landscapes into urban or industrial uses is often associated with urban sprawl.	(Arribas-bel & Sanz-gracia, 2014; Kemarau et al., 2024; Woltjer, 2014a; Yang et al., 2018b)
	Urban Form and Density	UfD	The physical structure of urban growth, including its density and expansion into previously non-urban areas, is significant.	(Arribas-bel & Sanz-gracia, 2014; Dadashpoor & Shahhossein, 2024)

2) Analysis cluster. The research further incorporates the application of cluster analysis, particularly using the K-means clustering method. K-means clustering is well-suited for categorizing districts within the Mebidangro region based on shared attributes that influence urban development. The method's key advantage, as noted by (Handayani, 2013; Raharja et al., 2020), lies in its ability to allow comparisons across different periods, which is crucial for understanding the evolution of urban systems over time. Data standardization with Z-score values weighs each Xi variable's value against the X variable's average (Handayani, 2013). Z-score ensures that cluster analysis reflects the data structure proportionally and is not affected by the scale of different variables. K-means clustering groups districts with similar socio-economic and physical characteristics into distinct clusters, facilitating the identification of different urban typologies. This methodology also supports the creation of typologies based on multidimensional indicators, as highlighted by (Abrantes et al., 2017), which is particularly useful for understanding the region's urban occupation and settlement dynamics. Before entering variable data in statistical software, some things need to be done, including:

- Data collection and processing combined field observations and interviews with key local actors — including municipal officials and urban planners — with quantitative inputs drawn from secondary sources such as census records and interpreted satellite imagery. These sources were

organized into tables and thematic maps to show spatial patterns clearly. The thematic review compared socio-economic, physical, and environmental changes across Mebidangro between 2005 and 2023, highlighting areas of rapid expansion and those with slower growth.

- The K-means clustering approach was used to group sub-districts by their urban development attributes, revealing spatial and temporal patterns. The number of clusters (four) was chosen to align with the activity centers identified in the national spatial plan, enabling consistent comparison between 2005 and 2023. This cluster comparison exposed sub-district development trajectories and pinpointed the primary factors driving change in the Mebidangro Metropolitan Area.

3) Interpretation and Conclusion. These findings are synthesized into a comprehensive report outlining the key factors influencing urban transformation in Mebidangro. The report highlights areas of rapid growth, shifting districts, and recommendations for urban planning and policy. The results of this study contribute to an understanding of the urbanization process in rapidly growing metropolitan areas, offering valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and researchers working on similar issues in other parts of Southeast Asia.

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of the System Activity of the Mebidangro Metropolitan Area

The Mebidangro Urban Area is part of the East Coast Region, a lowland area covering 26,360 km², or 36.8% of North Sumatra Province. This metropolitan area consists of the city of Medan as the core urban area, the Binjai Urban Area, and the Deli Serdang Urban Area as the surrounding urban areas, forming the metropolitan area. Based on the plan, Medan City, as a core city, is surrounded by nine (9) other adjacent cities (Satellite City), namely Belawan, Binjai, Sunggal, Tembung, and Bt. Kuis, Lubuk Pakam, Tj. Morowa, Pancur Batu, and Berastagi. Currently, Mebidangro has a concentric city form, with development starting from its center in the city of Medan and then extending to areas far from the center due to population growth. The interaction between land use and humans, both in economic, social, or political terms, thus forms several concentric zones. The constellation of the Mebidangro Area in the North Sumatra Province region plays the role of (see Figure 3):

Mebidangro Triangle –

SEI Mangke/ Kuala Tanjung

- National activity centre; Squir
- National and international gateway and distribution node, collector of goods & services, and international shipping lines.
- Regional transportation infrastructure: toll roads, eastern crossroads, Belawan Port, railway network, Kuala Namu airport.
- The development areas are the industrial, agricultural, tourism, and fishery sectors.
- National strategic tourism area of Lake Toba.

Figure 3. Mebidangro Regional Constellation Context of North Sumatra Province

- Sei Mangkei-Belawan-Medan Industrial Line: Belawan - Sei Mangkei goods distribution line (Program: Acceleration of the Kisaran - Indrapura Toll Road, integration with the train line)
- Lake Toba tourist traffic routes include Kualanamu - Sibisa and Kualanamu - Silangit (smooth road network Kualanamu - Lake Toba and smooth transit of Kualanamu - Lake Toba airport via Sibisa and Silangit).
- Development of areas in the agriculture, tourism, and fisheries industry sectors.
- Belawan Port and Kualanamu Airport within the Mebidangro Metropolitan Area.

Urban administrative areas are usually saturated and lack land and resources to support population growth. Hence, the population growth tends to be zero or even reduced, as conveyed (Woltjer, 2014b). Rapid population development occurs more in areas adjacent to Medan, leading to an increase in the surrounding administrative areas, which have high mobility to Medan during the day. The High Distribution of Urban Population is focused on the Medan City Area. It spreads southeast to the Sunggal, Percut Sei Tuan, Hamparan Perak areas, and Belawan.

In the Eastern Region of Mebidangro, there is a tendency for population growth, namely in the Lubuk Pakam area. Meanwhile, in the western region of Mebidangro, there is a tendency for the population to move towards Binjai City, while the western region of Berastagi serves as a sub-center of the city, focusing on food crop agriculture. The development of birth, death, and migration rates largely determines the population structure of an area. Therefore, if the birth rate in an area is high enough, it can result in the area being classified as a young population area (see Figure 4, Table 2).

Figure 4. Dynamics of Population Growth

The Mebidangro Metropolitan Area has a relatively even population increase in all activity centers. Still, the highest increase is in the urban core sub-district, spreading to sub-districts outside the urban core range, from 500 to 1,000 people/km². The core city and the surrounding satellite cities tend to experience a relatively high population increase of around 7,500 – 12,500 residents every 5 years. This period marks the beginning of urban expansion outside the boundaries of Medan City into the surrounding area. The fact that the population increase from the core city area extends beyond the core city limits can be a negative characteristic in the context of equitable growth in the Setelit Cities, as it leads to metropolitan monocentrism.

Figure 5 shows the distribution of agricultural areas in the Mebidangro Urban Area, totaling 36,234.13 Ha or 11.41% of the total area. In the food crop agriculture subsector, Deli Serdang

Regency, the most significant part of the Mebidangro Area, has made a significant contribution to North Sumatra Province. Although some commodities have experienced a decrease in production, especially rice, corn, and cassava, when measured by availability figures, they still experience a surplus.

Table 2. Distribution of Sub-Districts Based on Population Density and Population Growth Rate

		Population Growth Rate		
		High	Medium	Low
Population	High	Medan City		
	Medium	Hamparan Perak		Patumbak; Sungai; Tanjung Morawa
	Low	Binjai City	Barusjahe	Pancur Batu; Percut Sei Tuan
		Dolan Rakyat		Galang; Gunung Merah; Lubuk Pakam; Namorambe; Bangun Purba; Deli Tua; Pagar Merbau; STM Hulu; Berastagi; Merdeka; Sibiru Biru.
				Batang Kuis; Beringin; Kutalimbaru; Labuan Deli; Pantai Labu; Sibolangit; STM Hilir.

Additional Detail:

Population :	Population Growth Rate :	Population Density :
High >1.000.000	High >0,014	High >100 person/hectars
Medium 100.000 - 1.000.000	Medium 0,007-0,014	Low <100 person/hectars
Low <100.000	Low <0,007	

Figure 5. a) Settlement Distribution in 2023; b) Agricultural Distribution in 2023

Cluster Dynamics in the Mebidangro Region

The development of the Mebidangro area between 2005 and 2023 shows a fairly straightforward spatial transformation. In almost two decades, the core area of the city, which was initially limited to nine sub-districts, including Medan Area, West Medan, Medan Baru, Medan Kota, Medan Maimun, Medan Perjuangan, Medan Petisah, Medan Tembung, and East Medan, or to be precise, dominated by Medan City, has now expanded to eighteen sub-districts. The change is more than a number; it paints a vivid picture of metropolitan growth spreading into Medan's suburbs. It reflects how natural population increases and migration reshape the area, prompting new neighborhoods, services, and businesses to emerge. As (Handayani, 2013; Haryo Winarso et al., 2015) note, People often move to urban and peri-urban zones seeking better opportunities, placing greater demands on local infrastructure and basic services.

This phenomenon aligns with the view (Handayani, 2013; Woltjer, 2014) that migration is not just a physical movement, but also a search for opportunities. People come to the city because of the opportunities and expectations of better jobs, education, or access, while leaving the village spaces that have been the basis of agrarian life. As affirmed by (Woltjer, 2014a; Yang et al., 2018b), the shift in the structure of employment from agriculture to industry and services marks a fundamental change in the peri-urban economy. This change is not only a matter of employment statistics but also reflects changes in the lifestyles, values, and aspirations of people in suburban areas. However, rapid changes often exceed the capacity of the infrastructure (Farah et al., 2019b; Salvati & Zitti, 2017b), so the construction of roads, electricity, or clean water systems in peri-urban areas often lags behind the rate of physical growth. In Mebidangro, rapid urban growth has pushed into transitional zones faster than essential infrastructure has been prepared to support it. As a result, many areas are stuck in semi-urban conditions, characterized by dense buildings and populations, yet still lacking adequate public services.

When viewed from the city development plan of the Medan City satellite area, the past two decades have shown development that is not too significant. However, these nine locations can become the axis of Metropolitan development spread across the Mebidangro area. This satellite city is a fulcrum for future economic growth and a counterbalance to population pressure in Medan City. The differences in the development focus of each satellite city can create unique metropolitan dynamics. Medan Belawan serves as an industrial-logistics port city, Medan Sunggal is a new urban node offering dense housing and higher education, Medan Tembung is a growth gateway to Deli Serdang for service trade and vertical housing functions, and Binjai City has the potential to be a counter-magnet, while Bt. Kuis, Lubuk Pakam, Tj. Morowa and Pancur Batu were in the hinterland or peri-urban zone both in 2005 and in 2023, so there is great potential to strengthen their role as logistics nodes, higher education centers, vertical settlement areas, and manufacturing industries. In contrast to Berastagi, which is consistently in a specific agrarian cluster (highland area) in both 2005 and 2023, it is more appropriate to focus on strengthening it as a tourist destination and developing farmers, as well as supporting services for the green economy, thereby strengthening its character as a satellite city based on nature and culture. Therefore, the development strategy should consider the principle of tiered and layered metropolises, where the core city is strongly connected to satellite nodes through the transportation of people and goods, as well as adequate education, health, and support facilities. The overall membership cluster can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 6.

Table 3. Cluster Membership before and after Metropolitan Designation

Region	Sub-District	Before the Metropolitan designation		After the Metropolitan designation		Shifting
		Membership 2005		Membership 2023		
1	Medan	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core

2	Medan	Medan Area	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
3	Medan	Medan Barat	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
4	Medan	Medan Baru	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
5	Medan	Medan Belawan	3	Transition	2	Hinterland	Go down → Hinterland
6	Medan	Medan Deli	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
7	Medan	Medan Denai	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
8	Medan	Medan Helvetia	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
9	Medan	Medan Johor	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
10	Medan	Medan Kota	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
11	Medan	Medan Labuhan	3	Transition	2	Hinterland	Go down → Hinterland
12	Medan	Medan Maimun	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
13	Medan	Medan Marelan	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
14	Medan	Medan Perjuangan	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
15	Medan	Medan Petisah	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
16	Medan	Medan Polonia	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
17	Medan	Medan Selayang	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
18	Medan	Medan Sunggal	3	Transition	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
19	Medan	Medan Tembung	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
20	Medan	Medan Timur	4	Urban Core	4	Urban Core	Remain Urban Core
21	Medan	Medan Tuntungan	3	Transition	2	Hinterland	Go down → Hinterland
22	Binjai	Binjai Barat	2	Hinterland	3	Transition	Ride → Transition
23	Binjai	Binjai Kota	3	Transition	3	Transition	Remain Transition
24	Binjai	Binjai Selatan	2	Hinterland	3	Transition	Ride → Transition
25	Binjai	Binjai Timur	2	Hinterland	3	Transition	Ride → Transition
26	Binjai	Binjai Utara	2	Hinterland	3	Transition	Ride → Transition
27	Karo	Barusjahe	1	Agrarian	1	Agrarian	Remain Agrarian
28	Karo	Berastagi	1	Agrarian	1	Agrarian	Remain Agrarian
29	Karo	Dolat Rayat	1	Agrarian	1	Agrarian	Remain Agrarian
30	Karo	Merdeka	1	Agrarian	1	Agrarian	Remain Agrarian
31	Deli Serdang	Bangun Purba	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
32	Deli Serdang	Batang Kuis	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
33	Deli Serdang	Beringin	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
34	Deli Serdang	Deli Tua	2	Hinterland	4	Urban Core	Ride → Urban Core
35	Deli Serdang	Galang	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
36	Deli Serdang	Gunung Meriah	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
37	Deli Serdang	Hamparan Perak	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
38	Deli Serdang	Kutalimbaru	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
39	Deli Serdang	Labuhan Deli	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
40	Deli Serdang	Lubuk Pakam	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
41	Deli Serdang	Namorambe	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
42	Deli Serdang	Pagar Merbau	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland

43	Deli Serdang	Pancur Batu	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
44	Deli Serdang	Pantai Labu	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
45	Deli Serdang	Patumbak	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
46	Deli Serdang	Percut Sei Tuan	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
47	Deli Serdang	Sibiru-biru	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
48	Deli Serdang	Sibolangit	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
49	Deli Serdang	STM Hilir	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
50	Deli Serdang	STM Hulu	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
51	Deli Serdang	Sunggal	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland
52	Deli Serdang	Tanjung Morawa	2	Hinterland	2	Hinterland	Remain Hinterland

Figure 6. Transformation of Urban Cluster Members in the Mebidangro Region

In addition, the conversion of agricultural land also marks spatial transformation, and plantations are generally found in the Deliserdang area (including Bangun Purba, Pagar Merbau, Galang), Binjai (including South Binjai District, East Binjai), and Karo (in Dolat Rayat District). Land that used to be rice fields or gardens has changed its function to housing, factories, or trade centers. The face

of urban sprawl described by (Arribas-bel & Sanz-gracia, 2014; Woltjer, 2014a; Yang et al., 2018b). In Mebidangro, the decrease in sub-districts in the hinterland and transition zone clusters indicates an increasing need for agricultural space in suburban areas to accommodate urban development. If not carefully regulated and controlled, this process can threaten the food sustainability and ecology of the region.

On the other hand, not all regions follow the same current. Based on the results of the analysis, four sub-districts in the highlands of Karo Regency, including Barusjahe, Berastagi, Dolat Rayat, and Merdeka, have consistently remained specific agrarian areas from 2005 to 2023. The mountainous topography and the economic base of horticulture and tourism distinguish it from other lowland urbanization patterns in the Mebidangro area. In Karo Regency, the rapid changes in metropolitan cities are complemented by the firmness of the agrarian space, which maintains its own identity. This shows that the development of the Mebidangro metropolitan area is not uniform; there are still spaces with local dynamics and potentials that still survive.

Overall, the results of this analysis indicate that Metropolitan Mebidangro is moving towards a more complex and progressive metropolitan form since it was designated as a national strategic area. Urban expansion requires policies that can balance growth with control of sprawl. Regional transportation integration still needs to be strengthened to ensure connectivity between centers and suburbs, creating equal access. Hinterlands such as Deli Serdang need to be maintained as an agrarian buffer that produces semi-finished goods to add value. In contrast, specific agricultural areas such as Karo should be developed according to their unique potential. In this framework, Mebidangro regional planning responds to market growth and ensures it is sustainable, fair, and in favor of the character of each existing space.

Conclusion

Between 2005 and 2023, Mebidangro underwent a significant transformation that affected the physical characteristics of land use and its social, economic, and infrastructural fabric. The shift of cluster members from hinterland to urban areas reflects increased spatial integration and economic activity in various buffer regions. However, this movement was primarily driven by market forces and private investment, rather than by a metropolitan development plan that lacked operational guidance and applicable growth controls. The result was uneven development across the metropolitan area, increasing pressure on agricultural land, and infrastructure provision that lagged behind the pace and patterns of spatial change. Addressing these issues does not simply mean changing the landscape. Instead, the region must strengthen factors that increase productivity across core sectors—agriculture, plantations, manufacturing, and tourism. Achieving this requires better access to markets and services, improved transportation and information connectivity, systematic efforts to build human resources and technical capacity, and more transparent and predictable legal and regulatory arrangements. These measures enable investors and local actors to plan development confidently. In short, metropolitan success will depend more on the ability of each subregion to develop productively and sustainably, capitalizing on its comparative advantages, rather than becoming neglected suburbs or overburdened urban cores. To move toward balanced metropolitan development, Metropolitan Areas require a stronger and more practical governance framework that aligns planning and implementation across jurisdictions. Existing development plans must be transformed from high-level normative documents into actionable instruments that guide growth control and investment decisions. Cross-sectoral coordination—linking spatial planning with economic and social policies—will be crucial to prevent the concentration of benefits in a few urban centers and to spread opportunities across the region. Finally, further studies are recommended to examine how well metropolitan plans are being implemented, identify effective

intergovernmental cooperation models, and determine how local communities can participate in adaptive and inclusive urban growth. These lines of research can inform metropolitan systems that balance physical growth with sustainability, equity, and shared prosperity.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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